

Generalized State of Health Estimation Approach based on Neural Networks for Various Lithium-Ion Battery Chemistries

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ABSTRACT

The aging estimation of lithium-ion batteries is a central mission for a safe and efficient handling of lithium-ion batteries over the whole battery lifetime. However, especially the absence of precise diagnostic measurements within real-world applications yields the aging estimation a complex challenge. Moreover, the non-linear aging of lithium-ion batteries is strongly dependent on various operating and environmental conditions and the specific battery cell chemistry. This paper presents a generalized state of health estimation approach based on a neural network that can be used for different lithium-ion battery chemistries. The presented algorithm is able to estimate the aging of lithium-ion batteries by using information obtained from raw sensor data without executing further preprocessing or feature engineering steps. It is firstly shown that the developed temporal convolutional network accurately estimates the state of health for three different lithium-ion battery chemistries by only using high-level parameters from partial charging profiles. In addition, the obtained high-level parameters can provide relevant information needed for a battery passport. The final neural network is trained using transfer learning approaches to model the state of health development of a Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Aluminum-Oxide (NCA), a Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Manganese-Oxide (NCM) and, an NCM-NCA battery cell. The overall mean absolute percentage error of the generalized state of health estimation is 1.43%.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Hardware**; • **Batteries**; • **Computing Methodologies**; • **Modeling and simulation**;

KEYWORDS

Lithium-ion battery, Generalized state of health estimation, Deep learning, Neural network

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1 INTRODUCTION

In 2016, 195 countries agreed to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% until 2030 compared to 1990 due to global climate change [1]. To attain this objective, the usage of fossil fuels must be drastically diminished wherefore the renewable energies are coming to the fore [2]. For an efficient and sustainable utilization of renewable energy sources, reliable and safe energy storage is an indispensable prerequisite. The lithium-ion battery technology, with its high conversion efficiency provides an efficient technology as dynamic energy storage [3, 4]. Therefore, Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) are used in a wide range of applications from consumer electronics, electric vehicles (EV) [5], air- and spacecrafts to stationary energy storages [6, 7]. Depending on the power source, LIBs provide a great potential to reduce carbon emissions [8], especially within the transportation sector. However, the ecological, economic, and social implications of the whole battery value chain have to be further addressed. In particular, the intense growth in metals extraction, the sustainability of battery production as well as the uncertainties in the battery end-of-life (EOL) treatment, safety, and recyclability are one of the most critical challenges [8]. In order to ensure a more sustainable battery life cycle and to harmonize the battery regulations, the European Commission provided a proposal to modernize the European Union (EU) legislation on batteries [9]. One of the main points that is addressed by the regulation's framework is to increase the batteries life cycle traceability and transparency. For this purpose, future battery management systems (BMS) integrated in a battery system with an energy content of more than 2 kWh, must provide information about critical battery state parameters like the state of health (SOH). The SOH corresponds to the current aging state of a battery. However, it is not specified in detail how the SOH of a battery should be estimated within real-world applications. As a result, there is a great scope for interpretation on how to estimate the state parameters and which data should be provided. With this work, a real-world applicable SOH estimation approach is developed that is able to fulfill the requirements according to new EU battery regulations.

Typically, battery performance and energy characteristics are decreasing over time (calendar aging) [11] and with accumulated usage (cyclic aging) [12]. Thus, aged LIBs store less energy and deliver less power compared to their initial states [13]. Hence, aged batteries can fail to meet application specific performance requirements whereby the functionality and safety of the battery's applications are endangered [14]. Therefore, an accurate estimation of the SOH

is essential for the safe and efficient operation of a battery system. Moreover, the accurate tracing of the SOH is critical for an optimal battery EOL treatment [15, 16]. However, the non-linear aging of LIBs is dependent on various operating and environmental conditions wherefore the degradation estimation is a complex challenge. In addition, the aging state is not directly measurable and can be only determined using specific experimental approaches or by using model-based methods [17, 18]. Within applications and during the battery operation, the experimental approaches are not applicable due to the lack of availability of specific diagnostic experiment procedures, wherefore mainly model-based methods are used to estimate the SOH of a battery. Typically, three different model types are used for modeling the LIB: physics-based models, empirical models, and data-driven models. Physics-based models, e.g., the Doyle-Fuller Newman model enable an accurate spatially resolved simulation of a LIB [19]. These models are based on partial differential equations that describe the mass and charge transport as well as the charge transfer within the battery cell. However, a main drawback is the need of elaborative parameterizations. Moreover, models based on partial differential equations are generally solved using numerical analysis approaches like the finite element method which is computationally intensive. Thus, physics-based models are mainly used for research of different battery phenomena as well as for battery design and prototyping. However, physics-based models are not appropriate for on-board aging estimations without using further model reduction approaches [20]. Empirical battery model approaches provide a better online capability. Equivalent circuit models (ECM) are the most prevalent and widely used empirical battery models [21]. Still, specific measurements have to be executed to calibrate empirical models. The requisite measurements are very time-consuming in order to achieve a precise SOH estimation over the whole lifetime of a LIB.

Whereas the previous mentioned battery modeling approaches require specialized measurements for parametrization, data-driven approaches are able to precisely map input data to an output without the need of executing specific calibration measurements. In addition, data-driven algorithms provide a good real-time capability. Previous publications have shown great results on estimating the SOH of LIBs using data-driven algorithms. Whereby the range of data-driven models used for LIB state parameter estimation goes from simple regression [22], support vector machines [23] to neural networks [24–28] and other machine learning approaches [29, 30]. However, just a few publications have addressed data scenarios of real-world applications, where only partial load profiles are available. Moreover, most data-driven approaches take several preprocessing and feature engineering steps into account [31–33] that are mostly not applicable for embedded devices like a BMS due to limited computational power. Since the SOH estimation has to be performed within the application and during the operation, where only limited memory and computing resources are available, the corresponding model has to be executable on dedicated embedded devices. In order to close the previous mentioned research gaps and to address this challenge, an aging estimation approach was developed that is able to accurately estimate the SOH of a Lithium-Cobalt-Oxide (LCO) battery by using raw battery sensor data of partial load profiles without executing further feature engineering steps [34]. With this approach, an efficient SOH estimation model is provided that is

capable for on-board operations and can be adopted and transferred to BMS applications. However, as the most previous mentioned publications, also this approach was only tested and validated using one single battery chemistry. In addition, data-driven algorithms typically require train and test data that fulfill homogeneity requirements regarding data distribution or availability of sufficient labeled data samples. Therefore, extensive aging data sets have to be gathered to provide enough data for model training which can be very time consuming and expensive. Transfer learning technologies can be used to combine information's from different battery data sets and provide a generalized aging model. Moreover, during the operation of LIBs within real-world applications, heterogeneous battery performance characteristics can be arisen. To provide a stable and accurate SOH estimation, even for different behaving batteries, a generalized SOH estimation model has to be established. In order to achieve a generalized SOH estimation model, the SOH estimation approach from [34] is further developed and tested using three battery chemistries: Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Aluminum-Oxide (NCA) and, Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Manganese-Oxide (NCM) and, NCM-NCA.

The aim of this work is to bridge the aforementioned research gap and provide a generalized data-driven aging estimation approach that only uses information from raw battery sensor data of partial load profiles. For this purpose, high-level parameters describing the battery cell and the corresponding charge profile are obtained. A neural network is developed using Bayesian hyperparameter tuning that is able to estimate the SOH without executing further preprocessing or feature engineering steps. The neural network only receives 16 parameters describing the partial charging profiles as input data. These parameters can be further utilized to provide a battery passport describing relevant developments of the battery cell. Furthermore, to derive a generalized model, the provided Source Model is trained using transfer learning approaches to estimate the SOH of three different battery chemistries. The achieved generalized neural network is able to estimate the SOH with a root mean squared error (MAPE) of 1.43%.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, the data set is described. In the subsequent section, the methodology of the SOH estimation is presented. Section 4 provides the results and discussion of the SOH estimation for three different LIB chemistries. Finally, the summary and outlook are given in the last section 5.

2 BATTERY DATA

The following work was executed using the open battery data provided by J. Zhu et al. [35]. The battery data contains three data sets corresponding to three different LIB chemistries. Each data set provides cyclic aging data with different aging scenarios. In total aging data of 130 cylindrical 18650 battery cells are allocated. The specifications of the battery cells are shown in Table 1. In general, all battery cells were operated with full cycles at a constant temperature. The batteries were cycled within temperature chambers to ensure constant and controlled environment conditions. In Table 2, the details of the different cycling aging measurement conditions are listed.

Table 1: Battery cell specifications of the used open battery data sets [35].

Battery characteristics	Battery Cell Data Set 1	Battery Cell Data Set 2	Battery Cell Data Set 3
Cell type	Cylindrical	Cylindrical	Cylindrical
Form factor	18650	18650	18650
Cathode chemistry	NCA	NCM	NCA-NCM
Anode chemistry	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Nominal Capacity	3.5Ah	3.5Ah	2.5Ah
Lower cut-off voltage	2.65V	2.5V	2.5V
Upper cut-off voltage	4.2V	4.2V	4.2V

Table 2: Cycling measurement conditions of the battery data sets [35].

Data Set	No.	Chemistry	Temp	Charge Current	Discharge Current	No. of Cells
1	1	NCA	25°C	¼ C	1 C	7
	2	NCA	25°C	½ C	1 C	19
	3	NCA	25°C	1 C	1 C	9
	4	NCA	35°C	½ C	1 C	3
	5	NCA	45°C	½ C	1 C	28
2	6	NCM	25°C	½ C	1 C	23
	7	NCM	35°C	½ C	1 C	4
	8	NCM	45°C	½ C	1 C	28
3	9	NCA-NCM	25°C	½ C	1 C	3
	10	NCA-NCM	25°C	½ C	2 C	3
	11	NCA-NCM	25°C	½ C	4 C	3

The environment temperatures during the aging experiments are 25°C, 35°C and 45°C representing common LIB temperatures within real-world applications [36]. The charging current rates and discharging current rates are determined using the nominal capacity of each battery cell, e.g., ¼C corresponds to 1.75A and 1C corresponds to 3.5A for the NCA battery cell, whereas 1C corresponds to 2.5A for the NCA-NCM battery cell. Each cycle of the aging measurements contains a constant-current constant voltage (CCCV) charging, a relaxation and a constant-current (CC) discharging phase. The constant-voltage (CV) step during charging is performed until a cut-off current of 0.05C is reached. The relaxation phase is 30 minutes for the NCA and NCM battery cells and 60 minutes for the NCA-NCM battery cells. In Figure 1, the voltage and current profile of the first cycle is shown for a NCA battery cell at 25°C with a charge and discharge current rate of 1C.

The battery cells are repeatedly cycled with the specifications according to Table 2 and the aging state is permanently determined

a) Voltage profile

b) Current profile

Figure 1: Voltage (a) and current (b) profile of the first cycle of a NCA battery cell at 25°C with a 1C charge and a 1C discharge current rate.

using the full cycle measurements. Typically, the aging state of a battery is determined using the SOH. The SOH can be quantified by considering the internal resistance of a battery or by considering the total battery capacity. In this paper, we will mainly focus on the $\text{SOH}_Q(t_i)$ which corresponds to the total battery capacity at time t_i as defined in the following equation

$$\text{SOH}_Q(t_i) = \frac{Q(t_i)}{Q(t_0)} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

where $Q(t_i)$ is the capacity at time t_i and $Q(t_0)$ is the capacity at the battery cells begin of life (BOL) at t_0 . The SOH_Q at time t_i corresponds to $\text{SOH}_Q(t_i)$ and is given in %. The SOH_Q maximum is 100% at the BOL of a battery.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Aging Estimation using Partial Charge Profiles

As mentioned before, a main challenge of determining the SOH_Q within real-world applications, is the dearth of specific diagnostic experiment procedures. Most applications are only operated within use case specific state of charge (SOC) areas. As a result, there are only partial load profiles available to perform state parameter estimations [34]. As a result, an on-board SOH_Q estimation approach must consider that only partial load profiles are available. Since the discharging of a battery is typically very dynamic, the charging process is often used to estimate the SOH_Q . In general, the charging process has reproducible and quasi-static properties [38]. Contrary, discharge processes are typically very dynamic and depending on the application does not follow a reproducible procedure. In addition, the charging process typically starts at an arbitrary SOC and ends at a SOC of 100%. Therefore, especially the upper part of a charging profile is reliable available over the lifetime of a LIB and is therefore better suited for SOH estimations.

Figure 2: Measured SOH_Q degradation profiles determined with full charging steps for all 130 battery cells.

Figure 3: Partial charge profiles used for SOH_Q estimation.

Thus, in this work, we use the upper parts of charging profiles to accurately estimate the SOH_Q for different aging scenarios and for different cell chemistries. In Figure 3, the charge profiles that are taken into account for the SOH_Q estimation are plotted for a NCA battery with ½ C charge current rate. The corresponding capacities are determined using the Coulomb counting approach. It can be seen that with increasing aging, the charging capacity decreases. The last measured charging step in Figure 3 corresponds to 80.1% SOH_Q.

Since embedded devices like a BMS only have very limited memory resources, it is inconvenient to store and provide every measurement point of partial load profiles. Considering a fast charge current rate of 3C for EVs and by only taking a partial charge profile from 50% SOC to 100% into account, a total amount of 30k data points must be provided for one battery cell, assuming a typical BMS sampling rate of 50Hz. Since battery systems can contain several thousand battery cells, this approach is not practicable for on-board applications. To tackle this challenge, we developed an SOH_Q estimation approach that only receives an input containing high-level parameters describing the charge process and the corresponding battery. The input data is comprising of two parts: a static part describing the battery cell chemistry and specifications and a dynamic part describing the aging development of the battery. Figure 4 shows, an overview of the proposed SOH_Q estimation approach. Moreover, the model input parameters used for estimating the SOH_Q are listed. The static part of the input data contains information about the battery cell anode and cathode chemistry. Furthermore, the upper and lower cut-off voltages as well as the nominal capacity provided in the battery specifications in Table 1 are used as static part of the input data. The dynamic part of the input data is determined considering partial CC charging steps. The lower and upper voltages of the charging step as well as the average charge current rate and average temperature are taken into account for the dynamic part of the input data. Moreover, the total capacity of the charging step, the charging time as well as the average SOC and average depth of discharge (DOD) are used as input. The total operation time of the battery and a quantization for the overall capacity throughput supplement the dynamic input data. In total 16 parameters, five static parameters and eleven dynamic parameters are used as input data for estimating the SOH_Q. The two main advantages of our approach are that all parameters can be provided without the need of extensive computational and memory resources. The static part of the input data is provided when the

Figure 4: Overview of the proposed generalized SOH_Q estimation approach

BMS is initially configured. In general, the dynamic parameters are measured and provided by a BMS during operation. Only the SOC range of the partial CC charging profile has to be specified and the BMS can automatically store the measured parameters once an according charging step is executed. The second main advantage is that with our SOH_Q estimation approach a generalized SOH_Q model can be achieved very easily since the input data provides the information about the battery cell chemistry and related specifications. In addition, the provided parameters perfectly match the requirements of the EU regulations regarding relevant information of a battery passport [9] and can be provided to a superordinate control unit.

After measuring the high-level parameters, a Source Model is developed and trained using NCA battery data. During this step Bayesian hyperparameter tuning is executed to achieve an optimal model architecture. Afterwards, the Target 1 Model is derived by fine-tuning the model parameters of the last layers of the Source Model. The parameters of the first layers are fixed during training with NCM data. In the next step, the Target 2 Model is fine-tuned using NCA-NCM battery data and a generalized SOH_Q estimation model is achieved that is able to accurately estimate the SOH_Q of the NCA, NCM and NAC-NCM battery cells. For training the Target 2 Model, only the last two layers are used for fine-tuning, whereas the first layers are preserved according to the parameters from the Source Model and the Target 1 Model. As shown in the results section, using this approach an aging estimation algorithm is obtained that can be used for different battery cell chemistries.

3.2 Temporal Convolutional Neural Network

The SOH_Q estimation model is based on a temporal convolutional neural network (TCN). TCNs are a type of convolutional neural networks (CNN) that can be used for time series forecasting. The TCN architecture has recently shown the potential, to outperform recurrent neural networks (RNN) or long short-term memory networks (LSTM) that are specialized to time series processing [40]. Especially with a better performance in terms of training efficiency, model size and accuracy, TCNs get very popular for time series forecasting problems [41] and are therefore used in this work.

3.2.1 Causal and Dilated Convolutions. Contrary to typical 1D convolutions, the TCN architecture uses causal convolutions. The kernel of a standard 1D convolution is centered around a specific value t and thus considers values from the past $t-1$ and from the future $t+1$. Whereas the kernel of causal convolutions is applied to the rightmost value t and thus only considers data of time t and earlier. In Figure 5, a schematic illustration of a standard and a causal convolution are visualized.

In a next step, the causal convolutions are adapted to dilated causal convolutions in order to provide an efficient data processing [42]. In Figure 6, a stack of dilated causal convolution layers is shown. The kernel size k is dilated using a dilation factor d , thus the output at t is dependent on input values from $d \cdot (k-1)$ previous data points. In this work, we have doubled the dilation factor with every layer of the TCN as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of a standard convolution of a 1D convolution and a causal convolution with a kernel size of $k=3$.

Figure 6: Stacked dilated causal convolution layers. The kernel size is $k = 2$ and the dilation factor d , specified for each layer.

3.2.2 *Residual Blocks.* To provide additional stability and performance, the TCN architecture is equipped with skip connections [43]. The skip connections are implemented using residual blocks that provide an output \mathbf{o} containing a superposition of the data input \mathbf{x} and the output of transformation $F(\mathbf{x})$.

$$\mathbf{o} = \mathbf{x} + F(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

Figure 7 schematically shows a residual block used in this work. Using residual blocks, the TCN is able to learn and optimize in accordance with the identity mapping which is beneficial for the training of neural networks [44].

3.3 Model Training

The SOH_Q estimation performed in this work can be interpreted as supervised regression task. Since we are considering different parameters over time, e.g., charge capacity and temperature and current, a multivariate supervised regression problem is given. The objective is to find an appropriate approximation \hat{f} for the function f that describes the mapping of the input vector \mathbf{x} to the output y . For this purpose, the network architecture, and the related model parameters Θ have to be adjusted and trained such that the corresponding approximation function \hat{f} fulfills [45]

$$\operatorname{argmin} \left| y - \hat{f}(\mathbf{x}, \Theta) \right| \quad (3)$$

The training of the TCN was performed using the gradient descent superior Adam algorithm. This gradient descent method uses momentum and adaptive learning rates to provide faster optimization convergence [46]. The chosen loss function \mathcal{L} is used to measure the deviation between model output \hat{y}_i and ground truth y_i and

Figure 7: Residual block used for the TCN architecture.

is described by the mean squared error (MSE) defined in Equation 6

$$\mathcal{L}(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

The number of considered data points is specified by n . The previously described TCN and training algorithm were implemented with Python 3.8 and Keras 2.10 using backend TensorFlow 2.10. The training and evaluation were executed using an Intel Xeon Gold 1634 CPU with eight cores and a NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU. The hyperparameter tuning, which is described in the following section was performed and tracked using the Weights and Biases framework [46].

3.3.1 *Hyperparameter Tuning.* Data-driven algorithms and especially neural networks are extremely sensitive to their model architecture, e.g., number of layers or type of activation functions. These parameters are called hyperparameters and have a great impact on the model accuracy and stability [47]. There are various approaches for optimizing hyperparameters of a neural network, e.g., random search or grid search, however these approaches are optimizing the hyperparameters independently of the previous computations [48]. Contrary the Bayesian hyperparameter tuning approach takes previous computations into account to optimize an optimal hyperparameter setting. Thus, a fast convergence towards an optimal hyperparameter setting can be achieved [49]. In this work a Bayesian hyperparameter tuning approach is used provided by the Weights & Biases framework [46] to compute a hyperparameter setting vector λ for the TCN model \mathcal{T}_λ . The objective of the hyperparameter tuning is to determine an optimal hyperparameter setting vector λ^* such that

$$\lambda^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{(\mathcal{D}_{train}, \mathcal{D}_{test})} \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{T}_\lambda, \mathcal{D}_{train}, \mathcal{D}_{test}) \quad (5)$$

Where \mathcal{V} describes the evaluation function of the loss \mathcal{L} computed by \mathcal{T}_λ on the training data set \mathcal{D}_{train} and test data set \mathcal{D}_{test} .

3.3.2 *Transfer Learning.* Most data-driven algorithms require train and test data that fulfill requirements regarding homogenous data

Table 3: Hyperparameter definition and final parameter setting of the TCN models

Hyperparameter	Definition	Final parameter setting
Kernel size	$\lambda_k \in \Lambda_k$ with $\Lambda_k := \{\lambda_k \in \mathbb{N}; 2 \leq \lambda_k \leq 10\}$	3
Learning rate	$\lambda_l \in \Lambda_l$ with $\Lambda_l := \{\lambda_l \in \mathbb{R}; 0.001 \leq \lambda_l \leq 0.01\}$	0.0015
Dropout rate	$\lambda_d \in \Lambda_d$ with $\Lambda_d := \{\lambda_d \in \mathbb{R}; 0.1 \leq \lambda_d \leq 0.5\}$	0.3
Residual blocks	$\lambda_r \in \Lambda_r$ with $\Lambda_r := \{\lambda_r \in \mathbb{N}; 2 \leq \lambda_r \leq 10\}$	7

distribution or availability of sufficient labeled data samples. However, in real-world applications, these conditions are not met. Therefore, approaches are needed that enable an efficient learning using information from related tasks and domains [50]. To ensure an accurate SOH_Q estimation of LIBs, a large amount of labeled aging data is needed which is often not available since time consuming and expensive data gathering have to be executed. However, with the use of transfer learning strategies, information and knowledge of various battery types and chemistry domains can be combined to achieve a generalized aging model. In a first step, the TCN is trained with source data to achieve a SOH_Q estimation model specialized to the source data set. Afterwards, the target data set is used to post-train the model. During the post-training only, the last layers are active for optimizing the model weights. Whereas the remaining layers are not active and stay unchanged. With this transfer learning approach, a generalized TCN \mathcal{T}_G based on \mathcal{D}_G is achieved by using information from the TCN \mathcal{T}_S specified on the source data set \mathcal{D}_S where $\mathcal{D}_G \neq \mathcal{D}_S$.

4 RESULTS

As previously specified, in this paper three TCN models are trained in order to achieve a generalized SOH_Q estimation model. The models only receive high-level parameters derived from raw sensor data. First, the Source Model is trained on NCA data. In a second step, the Target 1 Model based on the Source Model is trained on NCM data using the described transfer learning approach. In a last step, the Target 2 Model based on the Target 1 Model is trained on NCA-NCM data using transfer learning. With this approach, the Target 2 Model provides a generalized SOH_Q estimation for each of the three battery cell chemistries and all aging conditions. The models were trained and tested using approximately 90% of the data sets whereas 10% of the data set were used for validation. The hyperparameters considered for optimizing as well as the final hyperparameter setting of the models are presented in Table 3.

After optimizing the models using hyperparameter tuning and transfer learning, the evaluation was executed using the validation data set. To quantify the model performance two metrics are considered: the absolute percentage error (APE) and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE).

$$APE_i = \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \cdot 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$MAPE_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N APE_i}{N} \quad (7)$$

The three models are validated using all different cycling aging conditions provided by the three battery data sets. In Figure 8, the SOH_Q estimation results are presented for three cells from

each of the different battery data sets with the corresponding cell chemistry. To compare the accuracy performance of all three models for each aging conditions and for all cell chemistries, each model was evaluated with the validation data, even if the model was not initially trained with the corresponding data, e.g., the Source Model was only trained using NCA battery data but is also validated with NCM and NCA-NCM battery data. The SOH_Q estimations are plotted in (i). The black reference profiles denote the reference SOH_Q, whereas the colored profiles are indicating the estimations of the different TCN models. The corresponding APE is shown in (ii). The deviation of the reference and the estimated SOH_Q is illustrated as a function of references in (iii). In (iv), box plots, determined from the APE profiles are indicating the quantiles and minimum and maximum values. Figure 8 a) shows the SOH_Q estimation of the Source Model, Target 1 Model and Target 2 Model for a NCA battery cell cycled at 25°C with 1C discharge and 1C charge. In Figure 8 b) and 8c) the SOH estimation results are shown for a NCM and NCA-NCM battery cell cycled at 25°C with ½ C charge and 1C discharge current rate. In general, the Target 1 and 2 Models are providing good to very good results for all battery cells. Whereas the Source Model provides only good results for the NCA battery with a maximum APE of 1.88%. Since the Source Model was only trained on NCA data without executing further transfer learning the performance is very poor for the NCM battery with a maximum APE of 10.25% and NCA-NCM battery cell with a maximum APE of 20.88%. The Target 1 Model was trained on NCA data and fine-tuned on NCM data afterwards. As a result, the target 1 model provides the best SOH_Q estimation for the NCM battery with a maximum APE of 1.50%. In addition, the SOH estimations of the Target 1 Model are also very accurate for the NCA battery with a maximum APE of 2.63%. The Target 2 Model combines the information from the Source Model and the Target 1 Model and was fine-tuned using NCA-NCM battery cells. In figure 8 c) it can be seen that the Target 2 Model provides the best SOH_Q estimation for the NCA-NCM battery cells compared to the other models with a maximum APE of 5.42%. However, since only 9 battery cells were available with NCA-NCM cathode chemistry, the overall SOH estimation results of the NCA batteries (in total 66 battery cells) and NCM batteries (in total 55 battery cells) are in general better for all models.

Since the Target 2 Model is based on the Source and Target 1 Model that were trained on NCA data and fine-tuned using the NCM data, the SOH_Q estimation of the Target 2 Model is also good for the NCA and NCM battery. With a maximum APE of 3.26% for the NCA battery and a maximum APE of 2.19% for the NCM battery, the Target 2 Model shows very good generalization properties by providing good to very good SOH_Q estimations for three different

a) SOH Estimation Results for NCA battery cell with 1C charge current and 1C discharge current at 25°C.

b) SOH Estimation Results for NCM battery cell with 1/2C charge current and 1C discharge current at 25°C.

c) SOH Estimation Results for NCA-NCM battery cell with 1/2C charge current and 1C discharge current at 25°C.

Figure 8: SOH estimation validation results

Figure 9: Summary of the SOH_Q estimation for different aged battery cells with different cell chemistries.

Table 4: Overall MAPE of the three provided models

Model	MAPE
Source Model	7.50%
Target 1 Model	1.51%
Target 2 Model	1.43%

battery chemistries. In addition, since the developed model architecture only has approximately 1500 trainable parameters, memory of less than 200kB is required. Together with the ability to estimate the SOH_Q by only using parameters that are easily derived from raw sensor data, the developed TCN model provides an appropriate solution as accurate on-board SOH_Q estimation algorithm. In addition, since only fundamental battery usage data like voltage, temperature and current which is provided by every standard BMS is used as model input, the developed SOH_Q estimation approach is suitable for real-world applications.

To have a better interpretation of the model's accuracy, Figure 9 shows the MAPE of the SOH_Q estimations of the three models for ten battery cells, with different chemistries and aging conditions. The MAPE is presented for ten different aging conditions and the three different cell chemistries for the three provided TCN models. The x-axis provides the number of cycling aging conditions according to Table 2. As mentioned before, it can be seen that the Source Model only provides accurate SOH_Q estimations for the NCA batteries (group one to five). For the other groups only very poor results are achieved as expected since the Source Model was neither trained on the NCM batteries (group seven and eight) nor on the NCA-NCM batteries (group nine to eleven). Furthermore, Figure 9 indicates that the Target 1 Model and Target 2 Model perform very accurate on all different battery cells and aging conditions. Whereas the Target 1 Model provides the best results on the NCM batteries (group seven and eight), the Target 2 Model provides the best results on the NCA-NCM battery cells (group nine to eleven). For the validation cells from the NCA data set, the Target 1 Model performs slightly better than Target 2 Model. This can be explained by the training process. Since the Target 1 Model preserves more parameters from the source model than Target 2 Model as schematically shown in Figure 4, Target 1 Model contains more information about the SOH_Q development of NCA batteries compared to Target 2 Model. In Table 4, the overall MAPE of the three models are listed. Again, it can be seen, that the Target 2 Model provides the best overall MAPE over all validation battery cells with an MAPE of 1.43%.

5 CONCLUSION

In the presented work, a generalized aging estimation model was developed based on a TCN. First a Source Model was trained on NCA battery data and optimized using Bayesian hyperparameter tuning. In a second step, the model architecture and parameters were transferred to a Target 1 Model. This model was fine-tuned using transfer learning and by considering cycling aging data of NCM based batteries. In a final step, the Target 2 Model, based on Target 1 Model was fine-tuned using NCA-NCM battery data. All three models only receive high-level information about the

battery cell chemistry and partial CC charging steps. Whereas the information about the battery cell chemistry is static, the used meta data describing the operation of the cell is dynamic and changes with every cycle. It is shown, that with this approach, an accurate generalized SOH_Q estimation algorithm can be provided with an overall MAPE of 1.43% over all cycling conditions and considered battery cell chemistries.

The two main contributions of this work are the development of an aging estimation approach that combines information about the cell chemistry and information about partial CC charge profiles, that can be simply derived from raw sensor data during a CC partial charge step. Contrary to related works [25, 34], with this approach only a small amount of easily accessible data has to be provided to precisely estimate the SOH_Q and is thus suitable for on-board applications like a BMS. Moreover, with this approach, relevant data describing the battery cells aging state, can be provided to a battery passport required by the EU's battery regulation framework. The second main contribution is the achievement of a generalized aging estimation model based on a TCN. By using the described transfer learning approach together with the developed aging estimation approach, the final model precisely estimates the SOH_Q for three different LIB chemistries.

Since we focused on battery cell chemistries with similar compositions, future studies will focus on the investigation of the suitability of the provided approach to different battery cell chemistries, e.g., LFP based LIBs. In addition, the provided static and dynamic battery parameters will be further investigated and developed to provide a holistic parameter set that can be easily obtained on the one side and accurately describes the battery aging trajectory on the other side. Furthermore, the developed approach will be benchmarked with other machine learning algorithms in terms of accuracy and resources consumption. Finally, the developed approach will be tested and validated within real-world applications. Therefore, the model will be transferred to a BMS integrated into a commercial EV and tested under real-world conditions.

AUTHORSHIP

Steffen Bockrath: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing, Visualization, Review & editing.
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